

Supporting Information

Aspects of Gas Storage: Confined Geometry Effects on the High-Pressure Adsorption Behavior of Supercritical Fluids

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Figure S1: Surface excess and (absolute) adsorbed amount (obtained by assuming that the entire pore-volume encounters as adsorbate space) of C₂H₄ on NaY (1.1), SBA-3 (2.5), MCM-48 (3.8) and KIT-6 (10.5) at 15°C.

Figure S2: High-pressure surface excess isotherms of CH₄ on NaY RM8850 at 25°C. The expected reference value is given as solid black line, while the 95 % uncertainty interval is restricted by dashed lines ¹.

Figure S3: High-resolution C₂H₄ surface excess isotherms at $T_{red} = 1.038$ obtained on the micro- and mesoporous model materials. The reduced density of the bulk fluid corresponding to the experimental conditions is given as black dashed line.

Figure S4: High-resolution C₂H₄ surface excess isotherms at $T_{red} = 1.056$ obtained on the micro- and mesoporous model materials. The reduced density of the bulk fluid corresponding to the experimental conditions is given as black dashed line.

Figure S5: Derivative of the bulk density ρ of C_2H_4 at various reduced temperatures with regard to the reduced pressure p_{red} .

Figure S6: High-resolution low-pressure (absolute) adsorbed isotherms of C_2H_4 on CPG (18.5) at various temperatures showed up to a reduced pressure of 0.2 (corresponding to about 10 bar). For deriving isochoric data, the isotherm data could be in this case well fitted with the sips-isotherm model.

Figure S7: C_2H_4 adsorption isochores on CPG (18.5).

Figure S8: High-resolution low-pressure (absolute) adsorbed isotherms of CO_2 on CPG (18.5) at various temperatures showed up to a reduced pressure of 0.2 (corresponding to about 14 bar). For deriving isochoric data, the isotherm data could be in this case well fitted with the sips-isotherm model.

Figure S9: CO₂ adsorption isochores on CPG (18.5).

Figure S10: High-resolution low-pressure (absolute) adsorbed isotherms of SF₆ on CPG (18.5) at various temperatures showed up to a reduced pressure of 0.2 (corresponding to about 9 bar). For deriving isochoric data, the isotherm data could be in this case well fitted with the sips-isotherm model.

Figure S11: SF₆ adsorption isochores on CPG (18.5).

Figure S12: Experimental determined C₂H₄, CO₂ and SF₆ heat of adsorption on CPG (18.5).

$$\delta_{blank}(p) = a \exp(bp) + \frac{c}{\sqrt{2\pi d}} \exp\left(-0.5 \left(\frac{p-e}{d}\right)^2\right) \quad (1)$$

Table S1: Parameters used to interpolate the blank isotherm, which are modelled by equation 1.

	T / °C	a	b	c	d	e
$\delta_{C_2H_4}$	15.0	-0.001	0.045	0.53	1.6	58
	20.0	-0.001	0.025	-0.2	3	63
	25.0	0.00001	0.1	-0.1	30	55
δ_{CO_2}	38.0	-0.001	0.032	0.045	2.6	80
	43.2	-0.001	0.034	0.045	2.6	84
	48.2	-0.001	0.030	0.030	9	92
δ_{SF_6}	53.0	-0.0002	0.037	0.08	1	43
	58.2	-0.001	0.06	0.03	1.3	44.5
	63.4	-0.0001	0.06	0.06	3	49

Table S2: Structural parameters of silica² used to calculate the microscopic wetting parameter.

$\rho_s [nm^{-3}]$	$\Delta [nm]$	$\sigma_{SS} [nm]$	$\epsilon_{SS} [K^{-1}]$
44.2	0.22	0.27	230

Table S3: Potential parameters for C₂H₄, CO₂ and SF₆³.

Fluid	$\sigma_{FF} [nm]$	$\epsilon_{FF} [K^{-1}]$
C ₂ H ₄	0.4523	199.2
CO ₂	0.4486	189.0
SF ₆	0.5510	200.9

Figure S13: Reduced pressure where the isothermal compressibility of bulk C₂H₄ has a maximum for various temperatures as a function of $((T - T_c)T_c^{-1})^\nu$.

Figure S14: Reduced pressure where the surface excess isotherm exhibits its characteristic maximum C_2H_4 , CO_2 and SF_6 adsorption on mesoporous materials as a function of the inverse pore diameter, the fluids' kinetic diameters and the microscopic wetting parameter at $T_{red} = 1.021$ and $T_{red} = 1.023$, respectively.

Figure S15: Reduced pressure where the surface excess isotherm exhibits its characteristic maximum C_2H_4 and CO_2 adsorption on mesoporous materials as a function of the inverse pore diameter, the fluids' kinetic diameters and the microscopic wetting parameter at $T_{red} = 1.038$ and $T_{red} = 1.039$, respectively.

Figure S16: Reduced pressure where the surface excess isotherm exhibits its characteristic maximum C₂H₄ and CO₂ adsorption on mesoporous materials as a function of the inverse pore diameter, the fluids' kinetic diameters and the microscopic wetting parameter at T_{red} = 1.056 and T_{red} = 1.057, respectively.

Material Synthesis

For the synthesis of KIT-6, 5.1 g of Pluronic P123 were dissolved under intense stirring in 185.3 g of distilled water and 9.9 g of hydrochloric acid (37%) in a closed propylene bottle. After its dissolution, 5.1 g of 1-butanol (Sigma-Aldrich, 99%) were added in one shot. After that, the mixture was stirred at 35 °C for 1 h before adding 11 g of TEOS (98%) in one shot. Further stirring of this starting mixture at 35 °C for 24 h was followed by hydrothermal treatment at different temperature and time to alter the pore size of the samples. Smaller pores (5.7 nm) were obtained during the hydrothermal treatment under static conditions at 40 °C for 72 h, while bigger pore sizes (8.5 and 10.5 nm) formed during treatment at 100 °C and 140 °C for 48 h, respectively. The solid product was filtered and dried for 2 h at 100 °C and for 12 h at 140 °C afterwards. To remove the template, the as-synthesized powder was stirred in an ethanol–HCl mixture for approximately 1 h. The obtained product was filtered and then calcined at 550 °C in air. MCM-48 was prepared based on previously published procedure. 1 g of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), 4 g of Pluronic F127, and 67 g of ethanol (absolute) were mixed in a polypropylene (PP) reaction flask at 25 °C under vigorous stirring. After complete dissolution of the reagents, 213 ml of freshly prepared NH₄OH solution (2.9 wt%) were added in one shot and the mixture was stirred over night at 25 °C. The next day, 3.6 g of TEOS were added at once during vigorous stirring (1000 RPM), which was maintained for 1 minute, then the material was aged at 25 °C for 24 h in static conditions. The silica was isolated by centrifugation (10000 RPM for 20 min) and washed two times with distilled water and once with EtOH (techn.). After centrifugation, the powder was dried at air over night, then pulverized with a mortar and calcined at 550 °C for 5h to remove the template.

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SBA-3 was prepared by dissolving 2 g of CTAB in 100 g of distilled water and 47.6 g of hydrochloric acid (37%) while stirring at high intensity at 30 °C. TEOS was slowly added to the stirred solution using a dropping funnel and stirring was maintained at high speed at 30 °C for an additional 2 h. Afterwards, the sample was aged in static conditions over night at room temperature. After filtration and drying at 100 °C, it was refluxed in EtOH, filtered and washed with deionized water. Calcination was performed in a muffle oven at 550 °C for 8 h in air, employing a heating rate of 2 °C min⁻¹.

Low-angle X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectra of the calcined and powdered samples were acquired in an angular range of $2\theta = 0.5\text{--}6^\circ$, which was adjusted for the typical ranges employed for the respective silica materials, in steps of 0.013° using a PANalytical EMPYREAN diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, Malvern, UK). The signals were collected by a PIXcel3D detector (Malvern PANalytical) in reflection geometry (Bragg–Brentano HD) using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm) at 45 kV and 40 mA and the results are given in S17.

Figure S17: Low-angle X-ray diffraction (LA-XRD) pattern obtained for the ordered mesoporous silica materials a) KIT-6 aged at different temperatures b) MCM-48 (3.3) and c) SBA-3 (2.5). The data reflect a Ia3d double gyroid framework for the KIT-6 and MCM-48 materials and a 2D hexagonal pore framework for SBA-3 (2.5).

References

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